

Hydride-Induced Reconstruction of Pd Electrode Surfaces: A Combined Computational and Experimental Study

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Abstract:

Designing electrocatalysts with optimal activity and selectivity relies on a thorough understanding of the surface structure under reaction conditions. Here, we combine experimental and computational approaches to elucidate reconstruction processes on low-index Pd surfaces during H-insertion following onto proton electroreduction. While electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy clearly reveals pronounced surface roughening and morphological changes on Pd(111), Pd(110), and Pd(100) surfaces during cyclic voltammetry, a complementary analysis using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry excludes Pd dissolution as the primary cause of the observed restructuring. Using large-scale molecular dynamics simulations, we show that the surface alterations are related to the creation and propagation of structural defects as well as phase transformations that take place upon the formation of hydrides.

Introduction

The surface morphology of catalytic materials influences their performance, reaction kinetics and selectivity. Understanding and controlling surface structures throughout the catalyst's lifetime is thus crucial for optimizing overall catalytic activity. Atomic-scale relaxations and reconstructions of single crystalline surfaces occur in electrochemical environments, where the surface rearrangements dependent on the presence of adsorbates, electrolytes, and applied electrode potentials under real reaction conditions^{1,2,3,4}. Hydrogen-induced reconstruction has been extensively studied for metal surfaces in electrocatalytic reactions^{5,6,7}. Palladium (Pd), a noble transition metal known for catalyzing hydrogen-based reduction reactions^{8,9}, is particularly well-studied in this context^{10,11,12,13}. Among low-index Pd surfaces, the least stable (110) termination undergoes various reconstructions upon the dissociative chemisorption of H₂^{9,13,14}. Recently, variations of the surface morphology of Pd(111), Pd(100), and Pd(110) surfaces and their impact on the hydrogen evolution reaction activity were investigated using electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy (EC-STM) and density functional theory (DFT)¹⁵. However, the restructuring of Pd surfaces under electrochemical conditions has still not been fully understood, mainly due to subsurface hydride formation that induces local plastic

deformations, surface phase transitions, and nucleation of extended defects such as stacking faults and misfit dislocations.

This study combines experimental and computational approaches to elucidate the atomic-scale mechanisms of restructuring processes on Pd(111), Pd(110), and Pd(100) surfaces during potential cycling. In our earlier study, proton electro-reduction processes and subsequent hydrogen absorption resulted in strain,¹⁵ which can lead to surface rearrangements. Herein, ECSTM is used to observe hydride-induced morphological changes of these surfaces, caused by repeated potential cycling within the hydrogen underpotential deposition (H_{UPD}) and double-layer potential region. Importantly, we avoid potential ranges which may lead to additional morphological alterations, such as those from Pd dissolution or similar to roughening observed for platinum single crystals^{16, 17, 18, 19}.

Pd dissolution on polycrystalline surfaces and nanoparticles during Pd oxidation-reduction cycles has been investigated extensively^{20, 21, 22}. However, Pd dissolution during hydrogen insertion at potentials more negative than 0.2 V vs. RHE has not been thoroughly addressed. In their electrochemical quartz crystal microbalance (EQCM) study, Czewinski et al. could not differentiate the mass changes between absorbed hydrogen and (possible) Pd depletion, and only a mass increase was measured^{20, 23}. Here, we employed on-line dissolution measurements using a scanning flow cell in combination with an inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (SFC-ICP-MS) to quantitatively assess Pd dissolution during H ingress on the three investigated Pd bulk surfaces as well as Pd nanoparticles.

Besides surface dissolution studies, DFT calculations demonstrated that subsurface hydride formation induces morphological changes and strain in Pd surfaces¹⁵. However, these simulations are limited in system sizes and cannot completely capture the dynamics of realistic surface defects. Large-scale molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, enabled by advancements in machine-learning interatomic potentials²⁴, such as the atomic cluster expansion (ACE)^{25, 26, 27}, offer a solution with accuracy approaching that of first-principles electronic structure methods. Herein, we employ MD simulations using a highly accurate ACE potential to unravel the origin of H-induced reconstruction of the three low-index Pd surfaces.

Results and Discussion

Activity degradation of Pd(hkl) surfaces during the hydrogen evolution reaction

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was used to investigate surface changes of Pd(111), Pd(110), and Pd(100) single crystals. Their well-ordered structure was confirmed by recording CVs in Ar-saturated 0.1 M HClO₄, in the potential range from 0.2 V to 1.2 V vs. RHE, as displayed in **Fig. 1a**^{28, 29}. It must be noted that hydride-induced morphological changes were investigated with freshly annealed single crystals within the potential range of -0.18 V to 0.52 V vs. RHE. Cathodic potentials up to -0.18 V promote hydride formation, which starts at potentials smaller than the H_{UPD} potential region for bulk Pd surfaces.¹⁵ Additionally, the single crystals were not subjected to large anodic potentials to avoid surface oxidation. **Fig. 1b** shows Tafel plots, revealing activity trends for the three Pd single crystals. However, our focus shifts from activity comparison, already addressed in our previous work,¹⁵ to activity degradation along with increasing cycling numbers. Notably, Pd(111) and Pd(110) exhibited rapid activity declines after five and seven cycles, respectively. Moreover, **Supplementary Fig. 1** provides optical microscopy images for the post-HER cycling of all investigated single crystals. For Pd(100), despite initial stability, optical microscopy (10x magnification) after four cycles revealed significant morphological surface changes, including hills, grooves, and dimples.

Fig. 1 | Characteristic CVs of Pd single crystals and HER activity degradation. **a**, CVs of annealed Pd single crystals (Pd(111), Pd(110) and Pd(100)) in Ar-sat. 0.1 M HClO₄ recorded with 50 mV s⁻¹ scan rate. **b**, Degradation of HER activity with increasing cycle numbers, shown by Tafel plots (cathodic scan) for the respective Pd crystals in H₂-saturated 0.1 M HClO₄, recorded with 50 mV s⁻¹ scan rate.

In-situ investigation of morphological changes at Pd(hkl) surfaces

EC-STM permits visualizing gradual morphological changes at Pd single crystal surfaces during electrochemical cycling. As illustrated in **Fig. 2a**, after each cycling process within the H_{UPD} /double-layer potential region, we systematically recorded 150 nm x 150 nm EC-STM images utilizing a constant tip and sample potential in the double-layer region. A detailed description of all experimental parameters can be found in **Supplementary Table 1-2**. **Fig. 2b,c,d** display selected EC-STM surface images after the respective executed number of CV cycles on freshly annealed Pd(111), Pd(110), and Pd(100) single crystals. An overview of all intermediate surface snapshots and representative CVs captured during the cycling procedure are provided in **Supplementary Fig. 2-4**. The first EC-STM images (cycle 0) of the pristine Pd single crystals exhibit atomically flat terraces, confirming successful annealing procedures. As the cycling progresses, multiple-atomic structural defects (holes, steps, islands) emerge at terraces and in areas adjacent to step edges for Pd(111). Those defects are distinguishable by their lighter color compared to that of the smooth areas of the surface terraces. This color contrast is accentuated due to a larger range of the color bar for Pd(111) compared to those of the other terminations. For Pd(110), a complex surface structure appeared after eight cycles at the bottom of the image, reaching up to more than 100 nm in lateral size. However, with continued cycling, the structure gradually diminished, giving rise to nearby holes and hills. For Pd(100), the EC-STM image of the pristine surface (0 cycles) revealed the presence of an island, for which a roughly ~ 1500 nm² area partially disappeared after nine potential cycles. Furthermore, adlayers and holes emerged on top and adjacent to the initial island, which coalesced into valleys and hills after thirty potential cycles. In summary, islands gain both in lateral size and height, reaching up to several tenths of nanometres, with an increasing number of cycles for all investigated surface orientations.

Fig. 2 | EC-STM images highlighting morphological changes of Pd single crystal surfaces during potential cycling in the H_{UPD} /double-layer potential region. **a**, Schematic illustration of the EC-STM measuring procedure to explore hydride-induced morphological changes on Pd single crystals. Selected EC-STM images displaying the morphological changes on Pd single crystal surfaces; **(b)** Pd(111), **(c)** Pd(110), and **(d)** Pd(100) after varied numbers of CV cycles in the H_{UPD} /double-layer potential region. During image acquisition, an electrochemical neutral potential within the double layer was set. The number of completed CV cycles before capturing the EC-STM image is highlighted in green in the top right corner of each image.

For a more detailed analysis, we turn our attention specifically to Pd(111) and compare its morphology after thirty-four cycles to the freshly annealed surface, as displayed in **Fig. 3**. Despite a minor sample drift, we successfully maintained a comparable surface position for both images. The height profile, derived from a line scan at a position marked by a white line in the images, is plotted in the insets. Additionally, 3D visualizations obtained from the line scans are displayed in **Fig. 3c**, extracted from the 80 nm x 40 nm areas specified by the white rectangles in the 2D images in **Fig. 3a,b**. The EC-STM image of the pristine surface exposes two relatively high Pd steps with heights of 1.6 nm and 2.8 nm, respectively, and an atomically flat terrace in between. The two steps converge during cycling, leading to the formation of a hole (~5 nm deep) mentioned above, located in the vicinity of the second step. Besides the formation of the hole, the 3D visualization reveals the appearance of a large number of conspicuous spikes, underscoring a substantial increase in surface roughness at the Ångström level. The density and height of these spikes differ across different surface regions. Particularly, the areas adjacent to the steps and within the hole display more pronounced spike density and height compared to the terraces. To quantitatively assess this change in surface roughness, we conducted a detailed analysis of the EC-STM images of Pd(111) using a modified version of the root-mean-squared roughness³⁰. Our roughness calculation method reduces the influence of nanometre-sized morphological features, such as islands, holes, or steps, and instead accentuates the surface roughness at sub-nanometre scales along those features. A more detailed description of the roughness analysis is provided in **Supplementary Section 1**. **Fig. 3d** depicts the calculated roughness increase along the potential cycling of the Pd(111) surface. However, while EC-STM reveals morphological changes on the Pd surface, addressing the nature of this alteration remains a challenge. Generally, the formation of ad-atoms and ad-islands might be attributed to surface dissolution under potential control coupled with subsequent redeposition and/or hydride-induced surface reconstruction.

Fig. 3 | Roughness analysis of Pd(111) after potential cycling in the H_{UPD}/double-layer region. EC-STM image of the (a) pristine Pd(111) surface and (b) after 34 CV cycles. The white line indicates the position of the height profile shown in the insets. c, 3D EC-STM visualization of 80 nm x 40 nm regions highlighted by the white rectangles in the 2D images above. d, Roughness analysis results for the Pd(111) surface, illustrating two distinct patterns of roughness development over the CV cycles.

Investigation of Pd dissolution from Pd(hkl) surfaces and Pd nanoparticles

On-line dissolution measurements with the scanning flow cell (SFC) technique were performed to investigate if the restructuring of the surface observed by EC-STM is partly caused by the dissolution of Pd atoms. First, a potential-step protocol emulating the EC-STM experiments was carried out for the single crystals. The results presented in **Fig. 4a** show no dissolution for all surface planes. To exclude a spurious influence of short finite potential jumps in the protocol, a second potential sweep protocol consisting of successive cyclic voltammetry measurements was also carried out. As displayed in **Fig. 4b**, no dissolution could be detected in this case as well.

Fig. 4 | On-line dissolution experiments for Pd(hkl) surfaces and Pd nanoparticles. Electrochemical protocols (top panels) and dissolution profiles for the three Pd single-crystal surfaces (middle panels) and Pd/C nanoparticles with an average size of 4 and 14 nm (lower panels) in Ar-saturated 0.1 M HClO₄ for (a) the potential-step protocol and (b) the cyclic voltammetry protocol. The black arrows indicate the observed dissolution peaks in the case of the measurements with nanoparticles.

Viola et al. measured dissolution from commercial 4 nm sized Pd/C nanoparticles using a cycling protocol with 0.03 and 0.60 V vs. RHE as lower potential limit (LPL) and upper potential limit (UPL), respectively³¹. In this case, dissolution lower than 0.003% of the total Pd

mass was detected. Since no dissolution was measured for Pd single-crystal electrodes, additional measurements were performed with Pd nanoparticles to address this discrepancy. First, analogous experiments to the work presented by Viola et al. were performed here with the same 4 nm nanoparticles and also with larger Pd/C nanoparticles of 14 nm. Small dissolved amounts were also detected using the current experimental setup, with higher dissolution for the 4 nm Pd/C nanoparticles (see **Supplementary Fig. 5**). The dissolution measured here is probably due to anodic dissolution at potentials close to the UPL (ca. 0.5 V vs. RHE) and therefore the tailing of the dissolution signal is still observed during the reverse scan. These results confirm the reliability of the online dissolution experimental setup used in this work. Pizzutilo et al. detected higher dissolution for a Pd/C nanoparticulate sample than for polycrystalline Pd, with an onset potential of dissolution that seems to be in line with the signal measured in this work, although an UPL of 0.9 V vs. RHE and a slower scan rate (2 mV s^{-1}) were employed in their electrochemical protocol²². The size-dependent dissolution observed in the present work is in line with the fact that the smaller nanoparticles are less stable than extended surfaces as described by the Kelvin equation (also known as Gibbs-Thomson equation in electrochemistry), according to which there is a decrease in the onset potential of dissolution/deposition by an amount inversely proportional to the radius of the nanoparticle^{32, 33, 34, 35}. For a direct comparison with the dissolution experiments for Pd single crystals shown in **Fig. 4**, the same protocols were also carried out for the nanocrystals. As shown in **Fig. 4a**, a slight dissolution is detected for the potential-step protocol at potential values close to the UPL. Only very small dissolution peaks can be observed for the cyclic voltammetry protocol (**Fig. 4b**), also once the maximum of 0.52 V vs. RHE is reached. In both cases, the dissolution rates are very low and, therefore, the exact correspondence between the electrochemical signal and the dissolution profile is difficult to determine because it can be greatly affected by the residence times of the dissolved ions near the surface. However, it is clear that the dissolution detected here is related to the low-extent oxidation of the Pd surface near the UPL and it does not occur at potentials where the hydrogen insertion/de-insertion processes take place. This rules out Pd dissolution/redeposition as the primary cause of the morphological changes observed with EC-STM.

Atomistic mechanisms underlying the H-induced Pd surface reconstruction

As the online ICP-MS measurements reveal no Pd dissolution during the excursions into negative potential values, the increased surface roughness and morphological changes observed by EC-STM should be attributed solely to H-induced surface reconstruction. To shed fundamental light into the surface restructuring process during hydride formation, MD simulations were performed for PdH/Pd(111), PdH/Pd(110), and PdH/Pd(100) slab models (see details in **Methods** and **Supplementary Section 3**). The surface structures after 8 ns MD equilibration at 300 K are shown in **Fig. 5a,b,c** and **Supplementary Fig. 8**. The simulations reveal the formation of defects (specified further and in **Fig. 5a-c**), surface restructuring and roughening for all studied surfaces, in accordance with the EC-STM observations. The roughening occurs already during the first ns for all three surfaces (**Fig. 5d**), with the roughness values of ~ 1.53 Å, ~ 0.94 Å, and ~ 0.27 Å at 8 ns for the Pd(111), Pd(110), and Pd(100) surfaces, respectively. The highest roughness observed for the Pd(111) surface is likely related to its close-packed structure and shorter interatomic distances between surface atoms as compared to the more open structures of the (110) and (100) surfaces³⁶. This can also be attributed to the observed lowest surface energy of the PdH/Pd(111) system after MD equilibration (see **Supplementary Fig. 7**). The PdH/Pd(111) surface is roughened by formation of adatoms, islands, and two step layers (**Fig 5a**). In contrast, two new Pd adlayers form on PdH/Pd(110) and this surface undergoes a missing-row reconstruction accompanied by formation of adrows, adatoms and vacancies (**Fig. 5b**). It is worth noting that among the low-index surfaces, the H-containing Pd(111) is the most stable surface³⁷. Moreover, the H-covered missing-row reconstructed surface of PdH/Pd(110) after 8 ns MD is more stable than the ideal one due to the exposure of the (111) facet³⁸. This explains the observed missing-row reconstruction of Pd(110) during hydride formation^{13, 14, 39}. In case of PdH/Pd(100), the surface roughening is induced by lifting some surface atoms and the formation of (111) facets (**Fig. 5c**). This indicates that also the Pd(100) surface tends to transform into the most stable (111) termination upon hydride formation.

During 8 ns MD equilibration, the surfaces reconstructed; H₂ formation, H diffusion and H ad- and absorption in thermodynamically preferred sites were observed (see **Supplementary Section 4**). In particular, the absorbed H occupies mostly the octahedral interstitial sites for all studied surfaces (see **Fig. 5e** showing the greatest number of H surrounded by six Pd nearest neighbours, with details of nearest neighbour analysis provided in **Supplementary Section 5**). Furthermore, the distributions of Pd and H atoms along the *z* direction (surface normal) were

evaluated for all surfaces (see more detail in **Supplementary Section 6**). As displayed in **Fig. 5f,g,h**, while the number of Pd atoms in each layer of the (100) surface remains the same as in the initial structure, it varies for the (111) and (110) cases. This corroborates the larger roughness observed in the (111) and (110) surfaces compared to the (100), which is caused by the transport of some subsurface Pd atoms to the surface. We observed that for all surfaces, some H atoms diffuse through the slab, eventually populating the opposite slab surface (**Fig. 5f,g,h**). Despite the disordered distribution of H atoms within the slab, there is a clear preference for the H atoms to stay on the surface. This aligns well with previous computational studies demonstrating stronger H adsorption on surfaces compared to absorption in subsurface interstitial sites^{37, 40, 41}. Details of H coverage and H diffusion are discussed in **Supplementary Section 6-7**.

Fig. 5 | Surface analysis of the equilibrated structures obtained from MD simulations. The reoptimized structures after 8 ns MD at 300 K with colour gradient indicating the atomic positions along the z direction for (a) PdH/Pd(111), (b) PdH/Pd(110), and (c) PdH/Pd(100). (d), Calculated root mean square (RMS) roughness of the three Pd surfaces as a function of simulation time. (e), Number of H atoms surrounded by different numbers of Pd nearest neighbours for the three reoptimized structures after 8 ns MD, which is normalized by the total number of H in each system. The nearest neighbour analysis for bulk PdH_{0.5} is also presented for comparison; (f,g,h) Distributions of Pd and H atoms along the z direction in these model systems, where dashed lines indicate the number of Pd per layer in the initial structures.

It is well known that the lattice constant of bulk Pd increases when it absorbs H; and formation of bulk Pd hydride results in a large lattice expansion⁴². Herein, we investigated extensively how the residual strains associated with the formation of subsurface hydride layers are related to the observed structural changes analysed after 8 ns MD equilibration. For the Pd(111) surface (**Fig. 6a**), the tensile strains in all directions are predominantly localized in the top-half of the slab where H atoms predominantly reside (see **Fig. 5f**). Such tensile strains thus occur due to the large amount of absorbed H and lead to displacement of some subsurface Pd toward the surface (see **Fig. 5f**) as well as creation of additional lattice defects (see **Fig. 5a**), resulting in the surface reconstruction and roughening. It is not surprising that the bottom-half of the slab, containing only a small amount of H, is under negligible strain. Interestingly, the boundary between the strained top and unstrained bottom halves is rather sharp. As shown in **Fig. 6d,g** and **Supplementary Fig. 13**, the reason for this abrupt change is a planar network of interfacial dislocations that accommodate the lattice misfit at the β -hydride(top)/ α -hydride(bottom) interface. These are common Shockley partial dislocations occurring on (111) close-packed planes in fcc metals^{43,44,45}. For the Pd(110) surface, there is no clear PdH/Pd interface and the tensile strains in the x direction is present over the whole slab, while expansive strains in the y and z directions are localized mostly in the upper-half sublayers, where H concentration remains higher (compare **Fig. 6b** and **Fig. 5g**). The strain in the slab is again relieved by formation of lattice dislocations, but these are positioned diagonally throughout the slab following the geometrical inclination of the (111) planes (**Figs. 6e and 6h** and **Supplementary Fig. 14**). In the case of the Pd(100) surface, large tensile strains occur only in the z direction normal to the surface and there are only very small strains along the x and y directions (**Fig. 6c**). This is consistent with the homogeneous distribution of H in the slab (**Fig. 5h**). No dislocations were detected in this slab (**Fig. 6i**) and only a small number of atoms with altered coordination exist near the surface to accommodate the rearrangement of some surface atoms into the (111) orientation (**Fig. 6f**). Thus, for 111 and 110 surface hydrides, it seems the relaxation is inhibited by dislocations, which is not the case for the 100 surface hydride where dislocations are absent after equilibration (**Figure 5**).

Fig. 6. Strain and dislocation analysis of the equilibrated structures obtained from MD simulations. The elastic strain (ϵ) for each Pd atom along the x -, y -, and z -axis (H atoms are omitted for clarity) of the reoptimized structures after 8 ns MD at 300 K for (a) PdH/Pd(111), (b) PdH/Pd(110), and (c) PdH/Pd(100), evaluated by determining the total deformation of the crystal around each atom, with respect to an fcc Pd with a lattice constant of 3.891 Å, where positive and negative values indicate the tensile and compressive strains, respectively; (d,e,f) visualization of the local structures and (g,h,i) dislocations in these model systems.

Conclusion

In summary, using EC-STM, we have detected a gradual roughening of the local morphology of the Pd(111), Pd(110), and Pd(100) surfaces induced by potential cycling due to proton reduction starting on an atomically flat surface. Online ICP-MS measurements show no Pd dissolution for all investigated surface orientations as well as for nanoparticles at potentials within the hydrogen underpotential deposition and insertion region. This indicates that the observed roughness and morphological changes of the Pd surfaces arise solely from the H-induced reconstruction. Through MD simulations, we have shed light on the dynamic rearrangement and restructuring of Pd surfaces after surface and subsurface hydride formation. This restructuring process requires a certain mobility of Pd and H atoms, which becomes obvious due to the creation of structural defects and phase transformations within the subsurface layers. This combined study provides both experimental and theoretical insights into the dynamics of electrocatalyst surface reconstruction under reaction conditions, with a special focus on PdH formation. Understanding these H-induced reconstruction processes of Pd surfaces is an indispensable prerequisite for the designs of highly active and selective electrocatalysts^{46, 47, 48, 49, 50}.

Methods

Palladium single crystal preparation and electrochemical characterization

For the conducted experiments, Pd(111) (\varnothing 6 mm, 99.999%, MaTecK, Jülich, Germany), Pd(111), Pd(110), and Pd(100) single crystal (\varnothing 5 mm, 99.999%, MaTecK, Jülich, Germany) disc electrodes were employed with a surface roughness below 0.03 μm and an orientation accuracy greater than 0.1°. To perform atomically accurate and contamination-free STM measurements, a thorough cleaning and annealing process of the single crystals is necessary before conducting the measurements. All glassware, TeflonTM pieces, and measurement cells were previously cleaned with “Caro’s Acid”, a 3:1 mixture of sulfuric acid (96% H₂SO₄ Suprapur, Merck, Germany) and hydrogen peroxide (30% H₂O₂, Suprapur, Merck, Germany). After cleaning with the acid, all pieces were washed multiple times with boiling ultrapure water (Evoqua Milli-Q (18.2 M Ω cm)). The electrochemical cleaning of the single crystals was conducted in a classical single-crystal cell consisting of a three-electrode setup connected to a VSP-300 potentiostat (Bio-Logic, France). For the electrolyte, 70% perchloric acid (Suprapur,

Merck, Germany) was diluted with ultrapure water to obtain a 0.1 M concentration. The employed 0.1 M HClO₄ electrolyte was purged with Ar (Westfalen, Germany) for 30 min. The counter electrode (CE) and reference electrode (RE) consist of a curled polycrystalline Pd-wire ($\varnothing = 0.25$ mm, 99.95%, MaTecK, Jülich, Germany) and a Mercury-Mercurous Sulfate (MMS) RE (B 3610+ from SI Analytics), respectively. Before EC-STM experiments, the cleaning procedure relies on conducting CVs (50 mV s⁻¹) in a potential range from 270 mV to 1270 mV vs. RHE. Subsequently, the respective crystal is annealed with an inductive heater (20–80 kHz, 15 KW– EQ-SP-15A, MTI, USA) to obtain a well-oriented surface. Annealing occurs in a continuously Ar-flushed glass vessel, where the Pd single crystals are mounted on a Pd wire in order to avoid contact with impurities. The annealing temperature corresponds roughly to 800–900°C for 60 seconds, followed by a cooling step at room temperature for 5 minutes. This procedure of annealing and cooling was repeated multiple times, however, with decreasing annealing times of 60 seconds, 50 seconds, 40 seconds, and 30 seconds, respectively. After the annealing procedure, the Ar-containing glass vessel containing the Pd crystal was transferred into a vacuum-proof chamber containing an Ar atmosphere before being inserted in the glovebox (Ar atmosphere), in which all EC-STM experiments were conducted, or in the SFC-ICP-MS setup for the on-line dissolution experiments. For the electrocatalytic experiments, the single crystals were annealed with a Heraeus Instruments RO 7/50 furnace. A detailed description of the annealing procedure, as well as the procedure for cyclic voltammetry and activity measurements on the single crystals can be found in our previous study¹⁵.

EC-STM

All EC-STM measurements were conducted using a Multimode Nanoscope V SPM from Bruker connected to a Bruker Nanoscope Universal bipotentiostat and a Nanoscope V controller, located inside a glovebox (GS ALPHA X-Line) filled with Ar (5.0, Westfalen, Germany) gas. After preparation, the respective single crystals were mounted in a self-made, waterproof sample holder basically consisting of a conductive base plate and a TeflonTM ring to avoid any leaking electrolyte. STM tips used in the experiments consist of a Pt-Ir alloy with 80% Pt and 20% Ir ($\varnothing = 0.25$, 99.9+%, MaTecK), which were produced by a mechanical cutting and pulling procedure⁵¹. Before EC-STM experiments, each tip was isolated by Apiezon Wax⁵² in order to reduce the exposure of Pt-Ir side surfaces, which could significantly contribute toward the faradaic current that would even exceed the tunneling current in case of too-large interfaces. For the CE, a curled Pd wire ($\varnothing 0.25$ mm, 99.95%, MaTecK, Germany) was employed, while for the RE, a self-made Silver-Silver Chloride (SSC) RE-setup was

developed, which is partially immersed in the center of the miniature cell of STM head. During all measurements, a Nano20 active insulation plate from Accurion is mounted beneath the STM to reduce vibrational artifacts in the recorded data. The experiments aim to investigate and visualize the hydride-induced morphology modification of the low-indexed basal planes Pd(111), Pd(100), and Pd(110). Therefore, reference STM images of the Pd crystals were captured from the freshly annealed or initial state of the material with applied potentials in the double-layer region, in which the absence of faradaic processes was previously validated. An overview of the respective potential ranges, applied during cycling, and the parameters chosen for the respective EC-STM images, including sample and tip potential, scan size and rate, and integral and proportional gain, can be found in **Supplementary Table 1**. Afterwards, a series of CVs were conducted within the specified potential region to initiate hydride-induced morphology changes. This potential range contains the H_{UPD} and the double-layer region for the respective Pd single crystals in 0.1 M $HClO_4$. In order to ensure uniform morphology changes across all single crystals, the potentials were carefully chosen and adjusted during the potential cycling so that the current densities across different single crystals are roughly comparable. **Supplementary Table 2** provides a list of the parameters selected for the respective CVs. We highlight that EC-STM images were recorded at stationary conditions, which means not during the potential cycling. Therefore, the same double-layer region potential used during the imaging of each pristine Pd single crystal was re-applied before capturing another EC-STM image. Despite our efforts to maintain the same tip location, it proved to be challenging due to the artificial noise and thermal drift arising over time during EC-STM experiments.

Palladium nanoparticles supported on Vulcan XC-72

For Pd/C nanoparticles with an average diameter of 4 nm, Pd/Vulcan[®] XC-72 catalyst with a nominal Pd weight fraction of 20 % was purchased from Premetek (item P30A200) and used as received. See **Supplementary Section 9** for additional characterizations.

For Pd/C nanoparticles with an average diameter of 14 nm, Pd nanoparticles were synthesized using a two-microemulsion technique, as detailed in the work by Moumaneix et al.⁵³ Briefly, two separate microemulsions were prepared, one containing a Pd precursor ($Pd(NH_3)_4Cl_2$, 0.1 M) and the other a reducing agent (hydrazine hydrate, Sigma-Aldrich, approx. 64%), both supplemented with the same amount of surfactant (AOT, Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 97\%$) and iso-octane (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 99\%$). Following thorough stirring, the microemulsions were

combined to yield Pd NPs. Subsequently, a carbon support (Vulcan[®] XC-72, Cabot) was introduced into the mixture before resolving the emulsion by adding THF. The resultant material was then separated and washed through centrifugation and dried overnight at 80°C before being calcinated at 250°C for 2.5 h. See **Supplementary Section 9** for additional characterizations.

ICP-MS

The electrochemical online scanning flow cell coupled to inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (SFC-ICP-MS) measurements were carried out employing an Ag/AgCl (sat. KCl, Metrohm) RE and a glassy carbon rod (HTW Sigradur G) CE. The reference electrode is placed after the SFC outlet to avoid chloride contamination. A previously reported optimized version of the SFC-ICP-MS system was used to fulfill the strict cleanliness requirements when working with well-defined surfaces⁵⁴. The working electrolyte was bubbled with Ar in a purge vial and was constantly fed using a peristaltic pump (Ismatec). The solution circulated through the SFC to the ICP-MS (NexION[™] 350X, PerkinElmer) by matching the Ar flow in the purge vial and the rotation rate of the peristaltic pump (MP2, Elemental Scientific) of the ICP-MS. A ca. 200 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ flow rate, carefully determined for each measurement, was employed. The dissolution of ¹⁰⁶Pd from the working electrode was tracked with the ICP-MS via previous calibration with Pd standard solutions (0, 0.5, 1, and 5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, Certipur, Merck). ¹⁰³Rh was the internal standard using a 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Rh solution (Certipur, Merck). The working area of the electrode in contact with the solution was 0.159 cm^2 .

Two electrochemical protocols were applied using a Gamry Reference 600 potentiostat. The working electrode was always contacted to the electrolyte at a controlled potential of 0.4 V vs. reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) in order to avoid any possible surface oxidation or hydrogen absorption before the measurement. The first protocol was a potential step program with sixty-second-long potential holds separated by 50 mV potential jumps, in which the initial potential value is 0.52 V and the final potential value is -0.18 V. The protocol was done backward up to 0.52 V, then repeated again to -0.18 V. The second protocol consisted of three consecutive CV cycles with a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} with 0.52 V and -0.18 V as UPL and LPL, respectively. All potentials in this work were converted to the RHE scale, and measurements were performed at room temperature (21 °C).

MD simulations

The Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) package⁵⁵ with the ML_PACE package²⁶ was used for MD simulations in this study. The interatomic interactions were described using atomic cluster expansion (ACE)²⁵ potentials, parametrized and iteratively trained for the Pd–H system based on a large, representative set of DFT calculations containing both elemental phases of Pd and H as well as binary structures of various compositions using the Pacemaker package²⁷. Details of the ACE model, its parametrization and computational benchmarks will be presented in a follow-up study.

Different Pd surfaces were modelled by cleaving the DFT-optimized structure of a bulk fcc Pd unit cell with the lattice constant of 3.891 Å, in the Pd(111), Pd(110), and Pd(100) facets. The surfaces were built with 20 layers for the Pd(111) and Pd(100), containing 576 and 512 Pd atoms per layer, respectively, and 28 layers for the Pd(110), having 384 Pd atoms per layer. To investigate the dynamical behaviour and the stability of PdH/Pd(hkl) interfaces, the three Pd surfaces were completely covered by one monolayer of H adatoms at the three-fold fcc hollow site, the long bridge site, and the four-fold hollow site for the Pd(111), Pd(110), and Pd(100) surfaces, respectively³⁷. For the initial structures, the upper half of all studied surfaces were fully populated with subsurface hydrogen occupying the well-defined octahedral interstitial sites⁵⁶. The resulting system sizes were Pd₁₁₅₂₀H₅₇₆₀ ($a = 66.03$ Å, $b = 57.18$ Å), Pd₁₀₇₅₂H₅₃₇₆ ($a = 62.25$ Å, $b = 66.03$ Å), and Pd₁₀₂₄₀H₅₁₂₀ ($a = 62.25$ Å, $b = 62.25$ Å) for the Pd(111), Pd(110), and Pd(100) surfaces, respectively. Before performing the MD production runs, an energy minimization with constant cell shape and volume of all structures was employed with LAMMPS using the conjugate gradient method to obtain the stable structures, where the stopping tolerance was set to 10^{-10} eV normalized on the systems' total energy and 10^{-10} eVÅ⁻¹ for the atomic forces. All MD simulations of the optimized structures were performed in the canonical (NVT) ensemble for 8 ns at room temperature (300 K) using the Nosé-Hoover thermostat with a temperature damping parameter of 0.05 ps. The time step in all simulations was 1 fs. The final structures after 8 ns were minimized maintaining constant cell shape and volume via the conjugate gradient method for subsequent analysis. The Open Visualization Tool (OVITO) software⁵⁷ was used for the visualization of surfaces, elastic strain calculation and dislocation structure analysis.

It is worth noting that the behaviour of H adsorption and absorption in Pd surfaces is dependent on the Pd lattice constant. Our previous work³⁷ demonstrated that the DFT method using the Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof (PBE) functional, with the van der Waals (vdW)-dispersion

correction (PBE-D3) proposed by Grimme et al.⁵⁸ provides the lattice constant closer to the experimental value, compared to the PBE one. Therefore, in this work, we analysed and reported the MD results obtained by the ACE potential that was trained on the samples of PBE-D3 calculations (ACE-PBE-D3 potential) in the main text. For comparison, MD simulations using the ACE potential without including the vdW correction (ACE-PBE potential) were also performed on the PdH/Pd(111), PdH/Pd(110), and PdH/Pd(100) slab models, constructed from a bulk fcc Pd unit cell with the PBE-lattice constant of 3.941 Å. These results are provided in **Supplementary Section 10**.

Data availability

All data in the main text or the Supplementary Information is available upon reasonable request. Source data are provided with this paper.

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Author contributions

A.S.B, S.C., M.V. and E.L.G. conceived and supervised the research. M.V. and M.M. initiated the computational collaboration. M.Q. and M.M. parameterized and developed the machine learning interatomic potentials (MLIP) with input from R.D. and the assistance of A.N. and M.V. Subsequently, A.N. and M.Q. performed molecular dynamics (MD) simulations under the supervision of M.V., M.M., and S.J.N.; A.N., S.J.N., and M.V. analyzed and interpreted the MD results. E.L.G., T.S., L.D., and A.C. conducted catalytic activity and STM measurements

with single crystals. V.B.-M. carried out the on-line dissolution experiments for the Pd single crystals and nanoparticles. T.K. and L.M. synthesized and characterized Pd/C with size of 14nm. A.V. and F.M participated in the experimental data analysis and scientific discussions. A.N., C.S., and V.B.-M. wrote the original draft with input from the other authors. All authors reviewed and edited the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

Supplementary Information: The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/XXX>.

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